

Cation Exchange and Selectivity Behaviour of Trace Elements Between Colloidal Clays and Resins in Aqueous-Alcohol as a Function of the Concentration of the Dispersed Phase

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To ascertain the role of ionic hydration, exchange studies have been made in aqueous-alcohol between varying amounts of H-resin and varying concentrations of clays associated with trace elements Nickel, Cobalt, Copper, Manganese, Iron and also with the monovalent element Lithium. Lithium is used to see the effect of ion-hydration on the ease of exchange. Selectivity co-efficients have also been calculated from the exchange data at different clay concentrations.

The exchange of ions and selectivity co-efficients are found to decrease with the concentration of the clay suspension. The rate of decrease is more prominent in aqueous-alcohol media than in pure aqueous medium alone. Dehydration caused by ethanol, increases the extent of overlapping of electrical double layers of clay particles and subsequently immobilizes the exchangeable ions to a greater extent.

Plants require some elements for their nourishment. Most of these elements are drawn from the soil by their roots. It is assumed that the plant roots can adsorb these ions from the surrounding soil by a process of ion exchange. Many attempts have been made to study these exchange property by using artificial means. Of these, the method adopted by Brown and Albrecht¹ and later on by Chatterjee² is very fruitful. Their method simulates almost soil-root system. It consists in having a H-system (clay or plant root) separated by a suitable membrane (colloidion or cellophane) from the soil colloid saturated with one or more kinds of ions. The membrane does not seem to interfere with the exchange. Moreover, the soil-root condition can easily be simulated. On the basis of their studies, Brown and Albrecht¹ and Chatterjee³ showed that ions on the clay surface differ in the ease with which they exchange with the H-ions of the root system. Chatterjee² and later on Nag and Chatterjee^{4,5} carried out exchange experiments between H-resin and clays saturated with common ions as well as trace elements usually found present in the soil.

The ease of replacement of the cations is known to depend on their size and degree of hydration. It is also known that in ethanol, in which the ions would be hydrated much less, if at all, the usual lyotropic series is reversed, so that ions are held in the order of their true ionic size and not in the order of their hydrated size. In order, therefore, to ascertain the role of ionic hydration in the exchange of the cations, experiments have also been carried out in aqueous ethanolic media. In the present investigation clays having exchangeable Nickel, Cobalt, Copper, Manganese, Ferric ion and Lithium ions have been studied in aqueous ethanolic media.

The selectivity co-efficients as defined by different workers^{6,7,8} are calculated by dividing the ratio of the concentrations raised to appropriate powers of two ions involved in the exchange reaction in one phase to that in the other. It is thus simply the equilibrium constant of the reversible exchange reactions, such as

The equilibrium constants respectively can be represented as usual by

$$K_{A}^B = \frac{[B^+]_R [A^+]_M}{[A^+]_R [B^+]_M} = \frac{[B^+]_R / [A^+]_R}{[B^+]_M / [A^+]_M}$$

$$K_D^C = \frac{[C^{2+}]_R [D^+]_M^2}{[D^+]_R^2 [C^{2+}]_M} = \frac{[C^{2+}]_R / [D^+]_R^2}{[C^{2+}]_M / [D^+]_M^2}$$

$$K_X^Y = \frac{[Y^{3+}]_R [X^+]_M^3}{[X^+]_R^3 [Y^{3+}]_M} = \frac{[Y^{3+}]_R / [X^+]_R^3}{[Y^{3+}]_M / [X^+]_M^3}$$

where the expressions in parenthesis denote concentration and subscripts R and M denote the two solid exchanger phases viz., synthetic resin exchanger and montmorillonite clay respectively. These quantities are also termed as selectivity co-efficients.

The selectivity co-efficients obtained either with one ion in the solid exchanger and the other ion in solution or with both the ions being present as exchangeable ions in the solid exchangers, are not expected to be constant, when concentrations are used in place of activity, although some of the workers have claimed to be so.

Fig. 2

In the present investigation, the complicating effects of complex formation is avoided, by selecting two solid exchangers, the resin phase simulating plant root and montmorillonite clay saturated with trace element cations. The selectivity co-efficients will obviously depend on the relative abundance of ions and their relative affinities towards the exchangers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The H-clay was prepared by following the usual method of electro dialysis by the clay fraction ($< 2\mu$) isolated from a sample of Gujrat bentonite and its b.e.c. was determined by KCl-KOH method of Ganguly⁹. Copper, Nickel, Cobalt, Manganese, Iron and Lithium clays were prepared by following the method described by Nag and Chatterjee^{4,5} in earlier papers.

Known amounts of the H-resin were taken inside a small cellophane bag, fastened at the end of a pyrex tube and moistened with water. It was then immersed into suspensions of base saturated clay salts of varying concentrations, contained in glass-bottles. The contents were covered by paraffin sealing in order to prevent evaporation of water from the bottles. The system was allowed to remain in this condition with occasional cautious shaking and the pH of the clay suspension was measured from time to time with a glass electrode till it became constant. The equilibrium was usually attained within 8 to 10 days but the arrangement was not dislodged before 12 to 15 days. The b.e.c. of clay, after exchange, was determined by KCl-KOH method of Ganguly⁹. The difference in the exchange capacity of the clay salt as measured before and after the exchange reaction determines the amount of cations replaced by the H⁺ ions of the resin.

Fig 3

The amount of H-resin was varied in such a manner that the total amounts of H⁺ ion associated with it corresponded to 0.5s, 1.0s, 1.5s, 2.0s respectively where S is the symmetry concentration.

The selectivity co-efficients $K_{H^+}^{M^+}$ where M⁺ denotes Li⁺, $K_{H^+}^{M^{2+}}$ where M²⁺ denotes Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, $K_{H^+}^{M^{3+}}$ where M³⁺ denotes Fe³⁺ are calculated from exchange data.

DISCUSSION

The nature of variation of ion exchange and selectivity co-efficients of the ions with the concentration of the clay and also with the amount of H-resin i.e., the concentration of H^+ ion in the resin phase are shown in figs. 1 and 3, and in figs. 2 and 4 respectively.

Section (a) of both fig. 1 and fig. 3 represents the amount of cation exchanged as a function of the symmetry concentration of H^+ ions in the H-resin. The slopes of the isotherm of all the systems are different from those of the ions as measured earlier. The curves for 0.814% Lithium and 1.86% Nickel are very steep.

Section (b) of both fig. 1 and fig. 3 shows the variation of exchange with the clay concentration in aqueous-ethanolic media having 50% ethanol. It will be observed that the rate of exchange falls as the clay concentration increases. This rate of decrease in the exchange of cations as the clay concentration increases is much greater in water-ethanolic medium than in water alone.

Two factors may be responsible for the above type of variation of exchange with clay concentration in the presence of ethanol.

(i) As a result of dehydration caused by ethanol, the electrical double layer of clay particles overlap to a greater extent and the exchangeable cations are immobilised, so to say, this tends to lower the exchangeability as the graphs show.

(ii) The decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium and a consequent lowering of activity, as a result of addition of ethanol to water, may also lead to the decreased exchangeability¹⁰.

The selectivity co-efficients when plotted against the clay concentration, [Figs. 2(b) and 4(b)] also show a decrease as the clay concentration increases.

Section (a) of both Figs. 2 and 4 represents the variation of selectivity co-efficients with the symmetry concentration of the H-resin used. Here also the same decreasing trend is observed. In most cases, the selectivity co-efficient values attain a more or less constant

value with increasing symmetry concentration. Moreover, in aqueous-ethanolic media the curves obtained for the variation of selectivity co-efficients with both clay and symmetry concentrations are found to be steeper than those observed in pure aqueous media.

This may be due to the reduction of ionic hydration in aqueous-ethanolic media which results in more pronounced overlapping of the double-layers as the clay becomes more concentrated⁸.

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